

A JOURNEY OVER THE OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE LANDSCAPE OF THE JRC BIG DATA ANALYTICS PLATFORM

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the open source software landscape of the JRC Big Data Analytics Platform, an on-premises platform developed at the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission to facilitate the provision of enhanced scientific support to the policies and priorities of the European Union. The platform provides a shared collaborative environment to link data, data services, data scientists, and thematic experts across multiple domains. This is required to address the scale and impact of societal challenges such as climate change, sustainable development goals, and artificial intelligence.

Index Terms— FOSS, cloud native, Jupyter, data science, spatio-temporal data, STAC

1. INTRODUCTION

The JRC Big Data Analytics Platform¹ (BDAP) is an on-premises cloud platform based on free and open source software stack. The platform promotes and facilitates the linking of data, data services, data scientists and thematic experts for generating policy relevant insights and foresight. Beyond the benefits of using open source software for backing the various platform services, open source software is also developed by JRC scientists to achieve transparency, reproducibility, and accountability regarding the generated policy relevant insights but also to ensure that the associated data analysis workflows can be easily deployed and reused on other platforms.

The BDAP platform finds its root in the JRC Earth Observation Data Processing Platform (JEODPP) [1] that has been initiated in 2016 to meet JRC needs following Earth Observation entering big data. Interestingly, one could argue that the Copernicus Sentinel missions made open Earth Observation data entering the big data era. In fact, this triggered the initiation of the Big Data from Space conference cycle in 2014.

The main requirements for the BDAP platform were (i) provision of web-enabled data and data services following JRC user requirements across multiple sites and scientific domains; (ii) reliance on free and open source software in a scientific context to achieve transparency, reproducibility,

and accountability as well as portability; (iii) provision of collaborative environments for knowledge and data sharing as well as foster projects across domains to team up; and (iv) deployment in the JRC Data Centre to comply with independence requirements and contribute to strengthening Europe's technological and data autonomy. Currently, 750 users distributed across all 6 JRC sites and directorates have registered to access BDAP services.

The BDAP software landscape is illustrated in Fig. 1. Each block of the landscape refers to tools and projects sharing some commonalities of purpose whether for provisioning a service or providing users with data science tools. Note that the full software stack except for 2 data science languages and associated software (MATLAB and IDL) consists of open source software.

This paper is structured following a journey over the BDAP software landscape and related federation of services after a very short excursion in its hardware landscape. Like any journey and given the limited space available, only selected areas will be toured. The hardware layer and base services are detailed in Sec. 2. Services for data sharing and collaborative working are detailed in Sec. 3. Data analytics services ranging from batch processing to dashboarding are presented in Sec. 4. Future developments and perspectives are put forward in Sec. 5.

2. HARDWARE LAYER AND BASE SERVICES

The BDAP infrastructure is located in the JRC Data Centre and benefits from low cooling costs thanks to the recycling of the cooling infrastructure of a former EURATOM research nuclear reactor. Commodity hardware is considered for all components of the platform (CPUs, GPUs, and hot storage). The BDAP hardware landscape is summarised in Fig. 2. The CentOS version 7 Linux operating system is deployed on all bare metal servers. Virtualisation of Linux machines is achieved with KVM (Kernel-based Virtual Machine). All services run within dedicated Docker containers in virtual machines or directly under CentOS. The local registry of all BDAP certified Docker containers relies on the Harbor cloud native repository. Micro-services and containerised applications requiring elasticity and scalability are orchestrated by Kubernetes.

¹JRC Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP): <http://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu>

Fig. 1: Software landscape of the JRC Big Data Analytics Platform. Each block of the landscape refers to tools and projects sharing some commonalities of purpose whether for provisioning a service or providing users with data science tools.

Fig. 2: Hardware landscape of the JRC Big Data Analytics Platform.

Automation of the deployment of any service is based on a combination of **Foreman** and **Ansible**. Monitoring of the services is based on **Nagios** with logs forwarded to **OpenSearch**.

The main storage service consists of storage servers equipped with Just a Bunch of Disks (JBODs) enclosure. The total storage space amounts to a gross capacity of 30 petabytes. This space is seen by the users as a single volume thanks to the CERN **EOS** (EOS Open Storage) distributed file system software and associated FUSE implementation as a mounted file system on Linux [2].

All public services of the platform are accessible from the internet. For those services requiring authentication, two-factor authentication is achieved thanks to **EU-Login**. Access to the platform services relies on **Keycloak** single-sign-on so that users do not need to re-enter their credentials when switching from one BDAP service to another. The user database is managed via a Lightweight Directory Access

Protocol (LDAP) service based on **OpenLDAP**.

3. SERVICES FOR DATA SHARING, DATABASES, AND COLLABORATIVE WORKING

The BDAP platform fosters data sharing among all users of the platform. This is achieved by centralising the download and management of data from various sources. Given that a location and time stamp are associated to most of the collected data, the Spatio Temporal Asset **Catalog** (STAC) specification was selected as common language to describe these data. The BDAP data catalogue browser² relies on the **STAC browser** to discover the data collections and their metadata. The data collections are categorised according to the **INSPIRE**³ or the **GEMET**⁴ themes. Data collections and their items are also accessible through an Application Programmable Interface (API) based on the **STAC FastAPI** python library. BDAP is also used as storage backend for the JRC Open Data Catalogue⁵ that promotes open access to research data produced and published by JRC.

The database service consists of a series of containerised database engines as well as database clients and tools. The main ones are reported in the corresponding box of Fig. 1: **PostgreSQL** for relational database management us-

²BDAP data catalogue browser: <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eu/data/stac-browser/>

³INSPIRE: <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/Themes/Data-Specifications/2892>

⁴GEMET: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet>

⁵JRC Open Data Catalogue: <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu>

ing the Structured Query Language (SQL) to interact with the database, **PostGIS** as an extension of PostgreSQL to support the storage, manipulation, and analysis of spatial data, **MongoDB** as NoSQL document-oriented database system, **SQLite** for serverless database management system, **Redis** as in-memory, NoSQL database management system, **DBeaver** as database administration tool, and **Qdrant** as vector database and vector similarity search engine.

The BDAP platform encourages collaborative working by design since it brings all users within a shared web-enabled ecosystem for data and data analytics. Besides systematic downloads performed on behalf of users, data can be downloaded by users themselves from white listed sites. They can also synchronise their own data thanks to the BDAP hosted **Nextcloud** service. Data can be uploaded outside BDAP via network file system or the File Transfer Protocol Secure (FTPS) service using a FTP client like **FileZilla**.

Versioning, issue tracking, management of projects are handled thanks to a self-managed community edition of **GitLab**. Note that open source software and libraries produced by JRC are available at <http://github.com/ec-jrc> and since fall 2022 at <http://code.europa.eu/explore>. The latter URL provides a code development platform for open source software projects for which European Union institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies hold the intellectual property rights.

4. DATA ANALYTICS SERVICES

4.1. Data science desktop (JEO-desk)

The data science desktop service provides access to a remote Linux Ubuntu desktop in a web browser. This is achieved using the Apache **Guacamole** clientless remote desktop gateway. The remote desktop is pre-equipped with numerous data science software environments. The data science languages and IDEs box of Fig. 1 pictures a selection of the main ones. Data scientists can configure their own environments in Python and R programming languages using **Conda**.

The BDAP data science desktop service also gives access to an instance of **ClearML**, a MLOps [3] architecture that helps users to develop and maintain machine learning models reliably and efficiently. ClearML has been selected among other MLOps solutions given that it offers numerous features while keeping a shallow learning curve. For instance, ClearML allows developers to keep track of different versions of a data set or a feature set, define a machine learning pipeline from data extraction to inference, run hyperparameters optimisation, and choose the best resulting model in an automated way.

4.2. High-throughput computing (JEO-batch)

The BDAP batch processing service (high-throughput computing) is based on the **HTCondor** workload manager that

is capable of orchestrating jobs running in Docker container thanks to its dedicated Docker universe. Docker containers matching the needs of each project in terms of libraries and software versions are created on demand and stored in the BDAP Docker registry based on Harbor. The batch processing service is directly accessible from the data science desktop service. High performance computing based on **OpenMPI** can be accommodated through a Docker Swarm under HTCondor and is also being tested under a Kubernetes cluster.

4.3. JupyterLab service (JEO-lab)

Jupyter notebooks are at the core of modern and collaborative data science [4]. Indeed, Jupyter notebooks provide a unified web-enabled interactive environment for coding in more than 40 programming languages with on-the-fly and on-demand code execution while integrating the code with data, visualisation, and documentation. The Jupyter project is continuously evolving and is now referred to as **JupyterLab**.

The BDAP JupyterLab service provides an interface for users to access their Jupyter notebooks within dedicated Docker containers offering pre-installed packages fulfilling user requirements. Some of the containers run on GPU servers so that they can leverage on their computational power for deep learning.

Regarding geospatial data, the interactive analysis is achieved thanks to a **interapro**⁶ [5] developed in C++ language and exposed as a Python package. The **interapro** library provides a highly parallelised tile engine that produces the tiles in real-time and deferred mode as needed by the map-view area managed by the **ipyleaflet** widget package imported in the Jupyter notebook. The rendering of each tile can be associated to arbitrary transformations using image processing packages such as **pyjeo**⁷ [6] developed at JRC. Upon setting an appropriate flag, the entire viewing area may be processed before tiling to avoid discontinuities at tile borders in case the processing involves neighbourhood operations.

4.4. Voilà as a Service (VaaS)

Exploratory visualisation combined with interactive analysis enabling the visualisation of data processed on the fly (lazy computation paradigm) rather than being precomputed are essential for modern data exploration and for conveying insights to a non-technical audience ranging from citizens to decision makers. Recent advances are moving away from dedicated web applications to data science environments supporting the creation of dashboards. In this context, the **Voilà** Jupyter plugin leverages on JupyterLab to turn notebooks into standalone web applications and dashboards.

⁶interapro library: <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/services/processing/interhelp>

⁷pyjeo: <https://github.com/ec-jrc/jeolib-pyjeo>

To enable users to autonomously and securely publish their dashboards, a dedicated service named Voilà as a Service (VaaS) has been developed and deployed on BDAP. Basically, BDAP users develop, test, and maintain their dashboards through a GitLab repository so that any push of the committed code to the master branch of the repository triggers the automatic deployment of the associated dashboard and publishes it with a dedicated URL.

In addition, the VOIS⁸ library [7] was developed to simplify the complex tasks involved in the creation of impacting dashboards while providing easy-to-use and reusable components without the need to delve into complex visualisation packages such as `ipyvuetify`. It can be installed from PyPI by issuing the command `pip install vois`.

5. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS AND PERSPECTIVES

The BDAP platform is continuously evolving to better serve user-needs and contribute to the generation of enhanced policy relevant insights capitalising from the collective knowledge of experts across scientific domains and their associated policy areas. The following developments are being tested and shall be available in production in the near future:

- base services: given that updates of CentOS version 7 will be discontinued at the end of June 2024, we will substitute it by **AlmaLinux**, an open source, community owned and governed, forever-free enterprise Linux;
- storage service: access with the **EOS S3 compliant REST API**. This will substantially ease the transparent and secure access through the HTTP protocol of the data shared on BDAP and referred to in its STAC data catalogue as well as in the forthcoming open-access JRC Research Data Repository;
- PostgreSQL data base service: disaster recovery with **Barman** and distributed databases with **CITUS**;
- JupyterLab service: evolution from in house implementation to **JupyterHub** or its SWAN [8] extension;
- visualisation service: deployment of Apache **Superset** as a service complementary to VaaS to allow users with no programming skills to explore and visualise their data and share associated dashboards;
- HTC and micro-services based processing: deployment of processing clusters relying on Kubernetes including the orchestration of data analysis workflows with **Argo**;
- AI model service: serve open source Large Language Models (LLMs) like **Llama 2 70B**;
- provision of isolated processing environments with data encryption.

Given that no one platform can possibly cover all user needs, links or federation with other cloud platforms are desirable. In particular, we aim at providing BDAP users of Sentinel data with the possibility to easily deploy their prototyped data analysis workflows on the Copernicus Space Data Ecosystem⁹ (CSDE). Similarly, links with European Open Science Cloud initiatives such as the EuroHPC¹⁰ will be investigated so that users can easily exploit the capacities offered by these initiatives by deploying their data analytics workflows from one ecosystem to another including seamless data ingress and egress.

Finally, the platform will be evolved to achieve compliance with the Infrastructure as Code paradigm while following cloud native principles wherever possible. This will ease the replication of selected services on other platforms to achieve higher availability and disaster recovery as well as facilitate interactions with complementary cloud platforms.

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⁸VOIS library: <http://code.europa.eu/jrc-bdap/vois>

⁹CSDE: <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu>

¹⁰EuroHPC: https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/index_en